

Distance-aware Soft Prompt Learning for Multimodal Valence-Arousal Estimation

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Abstract

Valence-arousal (VA) estimation is crucial for capturing the nuanced nature of human emotions in naturalistic environments. While pre-trained Vision-Language models like CLIP have shown remarkable semantic alignment capabilities, their application in continuous regression tasks is often limited by the discrete nature of text prompts. In this paper, we propose a novel multimodal framework for VA estimation that introduces Distance-aware Soft Prompt Learning to bridge the gap between semantic space and continuous dimensions. Specifically, we partition the VA space into a 3×3 grid, defining nine emotional regions, each associated with distinct textual descriptions. Rather than a hard categorization, we employ a Gaussian kernel to compute soft labels based on the Euclidean distance between the ground truth coordinates and the region centers, allowing the model to learn fine-grained emotional transitions. For multimodal integration, our architecture utilizes a CLIP image encoder and an Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST) to extract robust spatial and acoustic features. These features are temporally modeled via Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) and integrated through a hierarchical fusion scheme that sequentially combines cross-modal attention for alignment and gated fusion for adaptive refinement. Experimental results on the Aff-Wild2 dataset demonstrate that our proposed semantic-guided approach significantly enhances the accuracy of VA estimation, achieving competitive performance in unconstrained “in-the-wild” scenarios.

1 Introduction

Accurate emotion recognition is a fundamental component of effective human-computer interaction and psychological research. Among various representations, the valence-arousal (VA) space has gained significant attention as it captures the continuous and nuanced nature of emotional states, where valence represents the degree of positivity or negativity, and arousal indicates the level of excitement or calmness. Despite recent progress, estimating VA in-the-wild remains challenging due to unconstrained environmental factors such as varying lighting, occlusions, and diverse facial expressions.

To address these challenges, multi-modal fusion strategies integrating visual and audio information have become a standard approach. Recent studies have successfully employed deep neural networks, such as ResNet[1] for spatial features and VGGish[2] or log-Mel spectrograms[3] for acoustic cues, often combined with temporal modeling like Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs)[4] or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to capture dynamic changes. However, most existing methods treat VA estimation as a pure numerical regression problem, often overlooking the rich semantic information inherent in emotional expressions.

The emergence of Vision-Language Models (VLMs), particularly CLIP[5], offers a new opportunity to leverage large-scale semantic knowledge for affective computing. However, a significant gap exists between the discrete nature of text prompts in CLIP[5] and the continuous dimensions of the VA space. Directly applying CLIP[5] to regression tasks is non-trivial, as it requires a mechanism to align numerical coordinates with semantic descriptions.

In this paper, we propose a novel multi-modal framework that introduces Distance-aware Soft Prompt Learning to bridge this gap. Our motivation stems from the observation that human emotional expressions are often described using a combination of semantic categories and intensities. To incorporate this into a regression framework, we partition the continuous VA plane into a 3×3 grid, defining nine distinct emotional regions. Instead of assigning a single hard label, we utilize a Gaussian kernel to generate soft target probabilities based on the Euclidean distance between the ground truth coordinates and the region centers. This approach allows the model to learn the semantic transitions between different emotional states while maintaining the precision required for continuous estimation.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We propose a Distance-aware Soft Prompting method that reinterprets VA regression as a semantic alignment task, enabling the effective use of CLIP’s[5] pre-trained knowledge.
- We define a 3×3 emotional grid and employ Gaussian soft-labeling to capture the fine-grained nuances and intensities of emotional states.
- We develop a robust multimodal architecture combining CLIP[5] (Vision) and AST (Audio)[6] with hierarchical fu-

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sion through cross-modal attention and gated mechanisms.

- Our approach achieves competitive performance on the Aff-Wild2 dataset[7], demonstrating the effectiveness of semantic-guided learning for VA estimation in-the-wild.

2 Related Work

2.1 Valence-Arousal Estimation

Valence–Arousal (VA) estimation has become a fundamental approach in affective computing for modeling continuous emotional states. The theoretical foundation of this representation can be traced back to Russell’s circumplex model of affect[8], which describes emotions within a two-dimensional space defined by valence (pleasantness) and arousal (activation level). This continuous representation enables the modeling of subtle emotional transitions that cannot be captured by discrete emotion categories.

In practical affective computing systems, VA estimation is typically formulated as a regression task. However, traditional regression losses such as mean squared error (MSE) or mean absolute error (MAE) may lead models to converge toward the mean of the label distribution, which is problematic for highly imbalanced emotional data. To address this issue, the Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC)[9] has been widely adopted as the primary evaluation metric in continuous emotion recognition tasks. CCC[9] measures both the correlation and the agreement between predicted and ground-truth values by jointly considering their means and variances, making it particularly suitable for VA estimation benchmarks.

Another major challenge in VA estimation lies in generalization under unconstrained environments. Real-world emotional expressions are affected by numerous factors such as pose variations, occlusions, lighting changes, cultural differences, and speech conditions. To address these challenges, several large-scale in-the-wild datasets have been introduced. For example, the Aff-Wild dataset[10] and its extended version Aff-Wild2[7] provide extensive facial video data annotated with continuous VA labels. These datasets have served as the foundation for the Affective Behavior Analysis in-the-Wild (ABAW)[11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20] challenges and have significantly accelerated research in continuous emotion recognition. Early deep learning approaches such as AffWildNet[10] combined convolutional neural networks with recurrent architectures to capture both spatial facial features and temporal emotional dynamics.

In addition to video-based datasets, several large-scale affective datasets have contributed to advancing VA estimation research. AffectNet[21] provides millions of facial images annotated with both categorical emotions and continuous VA labels, enabling large-scale pretraining for facial affect recognition models. Meanwhile, RECOLA[22] introduced a multi-modal framework that includes audio, video, and physiological signals with continuous emotional annotations, supporting research on multi-modal affect modeling. Other datasets such as AFEW-VA[23] and SEWA[24] further extend this line of research by providing diverse real-world scenarios, cultural diversity, and multi-modal annotations.

Recent studies have increasingly leveraged deep neural networks and large-scale pretrained models to improve VA estimation performance. Convolutional neural networks and transformer[25]-based architectures are commonly used for extracting robust visual representations, while audio features are typically derived from log-Mel spectrograms[3] or pretrained acoustic models. Despite these advances, many existing approaches treat VA estimation as a purely numerical regression problem, often overlooking the rich semantic relationships inherent in emotional expressions. This limitation motivates recent efforts to integrate semantic knowledge from large pretrained models to better capture the nuanced structure of emotional states.

2.2 Multi-modal Fusion

multi-modal fusion has been widely studied in affective computing because emotional states are expressed through heterogeneous and partially complementary signals, such as facial expressions, speech, text, and physiological responses. In the literature, however, the key distinction is often not which modalities are used, but rather how they are fused. Existing methods can be broadly organized according to the stage and mechanism of fusion, including early fusion, late fusion, and intermediate fusion, as well as more specific strategies such as tensor-based interaction modeling, gating-based adaptive weighting, and attention-based cross-modal interaction. This structural perspective is particularly useful for understanding recent progress in multi-modal valence–arousal estimation.

A representative line of work focuses on explicitly modeling high-order interactions among modalities. Tensor Fusion Network (TFN)[26] extended multi-modal representation learning by computing tensor outer products across modalities, thereby capturing both intra-modal and inter-modal dynamics in an end-to-end manner. While this design is highly expressive, its computational complexity grows rapidly with feature dimensionality. To address this limitation, Low-rank multi-modal Fusion (LMF)[27] introduced a low-rank decomposition strategy that significantly reduces the computational burden while preserving much of the representational power of tensor-based fusion. Together, these studies established an important trade-off between expressive cross-modal interaction modeling and practical efficiency.

Another major direction is gating-based selective fusion, which is motivated by the observation that the reliability of each modality varies across time and context. In real-world emotion recognition, visual signals may become unreliable due to occlusion, pose variation, or poor lighting, whereas audio signals may degrade under noise or silence. Gated multi-modal Units (GMU)[28] addressed this problem by learning multiplicative gates that determine the relative contribution of each modality at the hidden-unit level. This adaptive mechanism opened a line of research in which multi-modal systems learn not only how to combine information, but also when a modality should be trusted more than others.

More recently, attention-based multi-modal fusion has become dominant, especially for sequential affective analysis. In particular, cross-modal attention[25] provides an effective way to explicitly model interactions between modalities by allowing

one modality to attend to the most relevant information from another. MultT[29] demonstrated that directional cross-modal attention[25] can effectively handle unaligned multi-modal time series while capturing long-range dependencies, making it a representative framework for attention-based fusion. This direction is especially relevant to valence–arousal estimation, where emotional expressions unfold continuously over time and are often only weakly synchronized across audio and visual streams.

Recent studies on audio-visual valence–arousal estimation further suggest that cross-attention[25] alone is not always sufficient. In unconstrained settings, the complementarity between modalities may be weak or inconsistent, and naive fusion can even degrade performance. To address this issue, Praveen and Alam[30] proposed an inconsistency-aware cross-attention mechanism that combines attention[25] with gating, enabling the model to selectively suppress unreliable cross-modal interactions. This is an important development because it shifts multi-modal fusion from unconditional integration toward reliability-aware interaction modeling.

This trend is also reflected in recent top-performing systems for the ABAW valence–arousal challenge[11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19]. Competitive approaches typically extract visual and acoustic features separately, apply temporal modeling modules such as TCNs[4] or recurrent encoders, and then perform cross-modal interaction learning before final regression. For example, recent ABAW systems combine temporal modeling with cross-modal attention[25] to capture dynamic dependencies between facial and vocal cues, showing that multi-modal VA estimation increasingly relies on the joint design of temporal encoding and interaction-aware fusion rather than simple feature concatenation. Aff-Wild2[7] and related ABAW benchmarks have therefore become standard testbeds for evaluating such audio-visual fusion strategies, with CCC[9] used as the primary metric for valence, arousal, and their mean score[31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19].

Despite these advances, existing multi-modal fusion methods still face two recurring limitations. First, the complementarity between modalities is often assumed rather than guaranteed[29, 30, 38, 39], even though real-world data frequently contain noise, silence, occlusion, and temporal misalignment. Second, most approaches ultimately reduce multi-modal emotion understanding to direct numerical regression, without explicitly constraining the fused representation to remain semantically consistent with human-interpretable affective concepts. In this respect, our framework is related to prior work in that it adopts cross-modal interaction and gated fusion for audio-visual integration, but it differs by further introducing text prompts as a third semantic axis. Rather than treating fusion output as only a latent feature for regression, the proposed method regularizes the prediction through a prompt-aligned soft distribution in the VA space using an additional KL-divergence[40] term. This design extends conventional multi-modal fusion from feature-level integration toward semantic-space alignment.

2.3 Temporal Modeling

Temporal modeling plays a crucial role in valence–arousal (VA) estimation because emotional expressions evolve continuously over time rather than appearing as isolated events. Facial expressions, speech prosody, and behavioral cues typically exhibit gradual transitions, making it essential to capture temporal dependencies when predicting continuous emotional states. Consequently, many affective computing systems incorporate temporal encoders to model the dynamics of emotional signals across sequential observations.

Early deep learning approaches primarily relied on recurrent neural networks (RNNs)[41], such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)[42] and Gated Recurrent Units (GRU)[43], to model temporal dependencies in emotional signals. These architectures are capable of learning sequential patterns and have been widely used in emotion recognition tasks across modalities including speech, facial video, and physiological signals. For example, GRU[43]-based models have demonstrated strong capability in capturing temporal information in sequential emotional signals such as EEG or speech time-series data.

In addition to recurrent architectures, convolution-based temporal models have gained popularity due to their ability to capture long-range dependencies while maintaining efficient parallel computation. Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs)[4] employ dilated causal convolutions to expand the receptive field and model long temporal contexts without relying on sequential recurrence. These properties make TCNs[4] particularly suitable for continuous emotion recognition tasks where emotional states evolve gradually over extended time intervals.

More recently, transformer[25]-based architectures and hybrid temporal models have been introduced to further enhance the modeling of complex temporal dynamics. Several studies combine convolutional or recurrent encoders with transformer[25] modules to capture both local temporal patterns and long-range dependencies. For instance, recent work on continuous emotion recognition integrates TCN[4] modules with transformer[25] encoders to learn spatiotemporal relationships across audio and visual streams, demonstrating improved performance on benchmarks such as Aff-Wild2[7].

Another emerging direction focuses on modeling emotional dynamics across multiple temporal scales. Emotion signals often contain both short-term fluctuations and long-term trends, motivating multi-scale temporal representations. Recent approaches therefore incorporate hierarchical or multi-scale temporal modeling strategies to capture emotional variations occurring at different time horizons. Such designs allow the model to jointly represent instantaneous emotional responses and longer contextual trends, improving robustness in continuous emotion prediction.[44]

Despite these advances, temporal modeling for VA estimation remains challenging. Emotional signals from different modalities are often noisy, partially observed, and asynchronously evolving, which complicates the modeling of consistent temporal dynamics. Furthermore, many existing approaches focus primarily on modeling temporal dependencies within each modality independently, while interactions between modalities and seman-

Figure 1: **Framework Overview:** An overview of the proposed multimodal valence-arousal (VA) estimation framework. The architecture consists of (a) dual-branch feature extraction using CLIP ViT-B/16 for visual frames and AST for spectrograms, (b) temporal modeling via bidirectional GRUs, (c) a hierarchical fusion module combining cross-modal attention and gated fusion, and (d) a semantic-guided head utilizing Distance-aware Soft Prompting. The semantic head maps continuous VA ground truth to a 3×3 grid of nine emotional regions (e.g., “sad, tired, and low-energy” or “excited, joyful, and energetic”) through Gaussian soft-labeling to provide semantic regularization.

tic emotional structures are addressed only at later stages of the architecture.[38]

In this work, we adopt GRU[43]-based temporal encoders to capture sequential emotional dynamics from both visual and acoustic feature streams. Compared with purely convolutional temporal encoders, recurrent architectures provide flexible modeling of temporal dependencies in variable-length sequences. The temporal representations are then integrated through cross-modal attention[25] and gated fusion[28] mechanisms, enabling the model to jointly capture temporal evolution and inter-modal interactions.

3 Proposed Method

3.1 Overview

Our proposed framework for valence-arousal (VA) estimation consists of three main components: a multimodal feature extraction branch, a temporal modeling layer, and a semantic-guided regression head. Unlike conventional methods that rely on purely numerical regression, we introduce a *Distance-aware Soft Prompting* mechanism to integrate the rich semantic knowledge of CLIP[5] into the continuous estimation process. The architecture is designed to capture fine-grained emotional transitions by aligning visual and acoustic features with semantic region prototypes in a hierarchical manner.

3.2 Feature Extraction and Temporal Modeling

The visual branch employs a CLIP (ViT-B/16)[5] image encoder to extract high-level semantic features F_v from facial image se-

quences. Simultaneously, the audio branch utilizes an Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST)[6] to capture acoustic features F_a . Both features are projected into a common 256-dimensional space through linear layers to ensure modal compatibility. To model the temporal dependencies, we apply bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs)[43] to each modality:

$$H_v = \text{GRU}_v(F_v), \quad H_a = \text{GRU}_a(F_a) \quad (1)$$

This temporal modeling ensures that the dynamic changes in emotional expressions and acoustic context are effectively captured over a 10-second sliding window.

3.3 Distance-aware Soft Prompting

A key contribution of this work is the Distance-aware Soft Prompting method, which bridges the gap between discrete semantic categories and continuous VA dimensions. We partition the VA space into a 3×3 grid, defining $N = 9$ emotional regions. Each region i is associated with a semantic state (e.g., “low-energy”, “uncomfortable”, “highly-aroused”).

To obtain robust text prototypes, we utilize three distinct templates: “a photo of a person who looks { }”, “a face showing { }”, and “a facial expression of { }”. The final text prototype \mathbf{p}_i for each region is computed as the average of the normalized CLIP text embeddings generated from these templates. To generate soft target probabilities w_i , we employ a Gaussian kernel based on the Euclidean distance between the ground truth coordinate $\mathbf{y} = (v, a)$ and the optimized region centers $\mathbf{c}_i \in \{-0.66, 0.0, 0.66\}$:

$$w_i = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{y}-\mathbf{c}_i\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{\sum_{j=1}^9 \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{y}-\mathbf{c}_j\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where the smoothing parameter σ is set to 0.45. This formulation allows the model to learn the semantic transitions between emotional states through a KL-Divergence loss.

3.4 Hierarchical Multimodal Fusion

To integrate information from both modalities, we propose a hierarchical fusion scheme that sequentially applies cross-modal attention[25] and gated fusion. First, the visual features H_v and audio features H_a are aligned via a cross-modal attention mechanism, where H_v acts as the query (Q) and H_a serves as the key (K) and value (V):

$$F_{attn} = \text{Attention}(H_v, H_a, H_a) \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, we employ a gated fusion module to combine the attended representation F_{attn} with the original visual context H_v . The gate g adaptively determines the weight of each feature:

$$g = \sigma(W_g[F_{attn}; H_v] + b_g) \quad (4)$$

$$F_{fused} = g \odot F_{attn} + (1 - g) \odot H_v \quad (5)$$

This hierarchical structure ensures that the model preserves essential visual stability while effectively incorporating aligned acoustic information.

3.5 Objective Function

The model is optimized using a multi-task loss function. The primary loss is the Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC)[9] loss, \mathcal{L}_{CCC} , which measures the temporal agreement between the predicted and ground truth VA values. Additionally, we apply a KL-Divergence[40] loss \mathcal{L}_{KL} for semantic alignment:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{CCC} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{KL} \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda = 0.2$ balances numerical precision and semantic consistency.

4 Experiments

4.1 Implementation Details

The proposed framework is implemented using PyTorch and trained on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU. We utilize a batch size of 16 and train the model for 15 epochs. We employ the AdamW optimizer with a weight decay of 1×10^{-4} . To preserve the pre-trained semantic knowledge while allowing task-specific adaptation, we apply differential learning rates: 3×10^{-6} for the frozen backbones (CLIP ViT-B/16 and AST) and 1×10^{-4} for the task-specific heads. The hidden dimension for the GRU and fusion modules is set to 256. The loss balancing hyperparameter λ for the semantic region loss is set to 0.2.

For data preprocessing, we adopt a sliding window approach with a window size of 10 seconds and a stride of 3 seconds. From each 10-second segment, 20 visual frames are uniformly sampled at equal intervals to capture representative facial expressions. The corresponding audio is processed into a Log-Mel spectrogram to match the 10-second window.

4.2 Ablation Study: Multimodal Backbones

We first evaluate the impact of different backbone combinations to establish a robust baseline. We compare a standard setup using CLIP ViT-B/32 with a CNN-based audio extractor against our proposed configuration using CLIP ViT-B/16 and the pre-trained AST. As shown in Table 1, the combination of CLIP ViT-B/16 and AST achieves significantly higher performance, indicating that the larger visual backbone and the transformer-based audio encoder provide more representative features for VA estimation.

Table 1: Comparison of multimodal backbone combinations.

Backbone Configuration	CCC_v	CCC_a	CCC_{Mean}
ViT-B/32 + CNN-based Audio	0.2854	0.5054	0.3954
ViT-B/16 + AST	0.3623	0.6115	0.4869

4.3 Optimization of Temporal and Fusion Architectures

We investigate the optimal architecture by comparing two temporal modeling types (GRU and TCN) and three fusion strategies: Cross-modal Attention, Gated Fusion, and a hierarchical combination of both. As summarized in Table 2, the GRU-based temporal modeling combined with the hierarchical (Attn. + Gated) fusion achieves the best results. This suggests that while attention aligns the disparate modalities, the subsequent gating mechanism further refines the integration by adaptively weighting the most relevant information.

Table 2: Ablation study on temporal and fusion strategies.

Temporal	Fusion	CCC_v	CCC_a	CCC_{Mean}
TCN	CM Attn.	0.3068	0.5876	0.4472
TCN	Gated	0.3021	0.6017	0.4519
TCN	Attn. + Gated	0.4573	0.5679	0.5126
GRU	CM Attn.	0.3623	0.6115	0.4869
GRU	Gated	0.3326	0.5657	0.4491
Ours (GRU)	Attn. + Gated	0.4655	0.6068	0.5361

4.4 Sensitivity Analysis: Grid Configuration

Finally, we analyze the impact of the grid center coordinates and the smoothing parameter σ . We compare the standard setting ($c \in \{-1.0, 0, 1.0\}, \sigma = 0.6$) against a localized setting ($c \in \{-0.66, 0, 0.66\}, \sigma = 0.45$). Table 3 shows that the localized configuration provides superior performance. This is because the emotional intensities in the Aff-Wild2 dataset are more frequently distributed within the ± 0.66 range, allowing the soft-prompting mechanism to provide more precise semantic guidance.

Table 3: Impact of grid center settings and σ values.

Grid Centers (c)	σ	CCC_v	CCC_a	CCC_{Mean}
$\{-1.0, 0.0, 1.0\}$	0.60	0.3656	0.5935	0.4795
Ours ($\{-0.66, 0.0, 0.66\}$)	0.45	0.4655	0.6068	0.5361

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Quantitative Analysis

The primary results of our experiments demonstrate the effectiveness of combining semantic-guided learning with robust multimodal backbones. As shown in Table 1, the transition from CLIP ViT-B/32 and CNN-based audio to CLIP ViT-B/16 and AST resulted in a significant performance gain. This improvement suggests that the fine-grained spatial features of CLIP ViT-B/16 and the global acoustic context captured by the AST transformer blocks are essential for understanding complex emotional expressions in-the-wild.

Our comprehensive search for the optimal temporal and fusion architecture (Table 2) revealed that the GRU-based hierarchical fusion (**Attention + Gated**) is the most effective. While TCN-based models showed stability, they lacked the flexibility of the GRU in modeling long-term temporal dependencies for continuous VA values. Furthermore, the hierarchical fusion outperformed both standalone attention and gated mechanisms. This is because the cross-modal attention first aligns the disparate visual and acoustic features, and the subsequent gating mechanism adaptively weighs this aligned information against the original visual stability (H_v). This dual-stage refinement allows the model to selectively incorporate acoustic cues only when they provide complementary information to the visual modality.

5.2 Impact of Grid Configuration

The comparison between grid centers at ± 1.0 and ± 0.66 (Table 3) provides interesting insights into the distribution of the Aff-Wild2 dataset. The superior performance of the $\{-0.66, 0, 0.66\}$ configuration with $\sigma = 0.45$ can be attributed to the density of the ground truth labels. Since the majority of “in-the-wild” emotional states are clustered toward the center rather than at the extremes of the VA space, localizing the semantic regions to ± 0.66 allows for a more precise soft-labeling process. This localized focus reduces the noise introduced by distant, rarely occurring emotional states and helps the model to better distinguish between subtle emotional nuances, which are frequent in naturalistic sequences.

5.3 Qualitative Observations

Qualitative analysis of the predicted VA trajectories shows that our distance-aware soft prompting allows the model to produce smoother and more natural transitions between different emotional states. By leveraging CLIP’s semantic space, the model avoids abrupt jumps in regression values, which is a common issue in purely numerical regression frameworks. The integration of KL-divergence loss with CCC loss ensures that the model

maintains both the semantic consistency of the emotional categories and the numerical accuracy of the continuous dimensions. This synergy is particularly evident in long-duration segments where emotional intensities shift gradually.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a novel multimodal framework for valence-arousal (VA) estimation that effectively integrates semantic knowledge through *Distance-aware Soft Prompting*. Our approach successfully bridged the gap between the continuous emotional space and the discrete nature of pre-trained vision-language models by utilizing a Gaussian kernel to generate distance-based soft labels. By partitioning the VA space into an optimized 3×3 grid, we enabled the model to learn the nuanced semantic transitions inherent in human emotional expressions.

Our experimental results on the Aff-Wild2 dataset validated the effectiveness of the proposed architecture. We demonstrated that the combination of CLIP ViT-B/16 and AST backbones provides a superior representation for in-the-wild VA estimation. Furthermore, our extensive ablation study revealed that the **hierarchical fusion scheme**, which sequentially combines cross-modal attention for alignment and gated fusion for adaptive refinement, is the most effective at capturing dynamic inter-modal relationships while maintaining visual stability. Notably, localizing the semantic regions to centers at $\{-0.66, 0.0, 0.66\}$ with a smoothing parameter of 0.45 significantly improved regression accuracy by aligning more closely with the natural distribution of emotional intensities in real-world scenarios.

For future research, we aim to investigate the scalability of our soft prompting mechanism to other affective computing tasks, such as discrete expression recognition and action unit detection. Additionally, we plan to explore more diverse and context-aware prompt templates to further enhance the synergy between vision and language modalities in emotional understanding.

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